

IOT AND ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE BASED SMART GARDENING AND IRRIGATION SYSTEM

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ABSTRACT

Most individuals don't have enough time in their busy daily schedules to practice gardening, despite the fact that it's essential to making cities green by maintaining rooftop gardens. In this project, we attempted to make gardening considerably simpler. By using this system, anyone can water the plant from anywhere in the world by just clicking their smartphone because it can water rooftop and balcony gardens both manually and automatically via the internet. The required hardware is a NodeMCU ESP8266, a 5V water motor, a 9V battery, a relay module, a rain sensor, a temperature and humidity sensor (DHT11), a soil moisture sensor (V1.2), and a soil moisture sensor (YL-69). This system will simplify things for gardeners who lack the time to water their plants by enabling them to do it from anywhere on earth.

Keywords: Iot, Irrigation, Gardening, Agriculture, Nodemcu ESP8266, DHT11, Sensors, Android Application, Artificial Intelligence, Rain Sensor.

I. INTRODUCTION

Planting is a healthy hobby that brings us closer to nature, and it is also profitable for both mind and fitness. But in our day-to-day busy lives, it is so difficult to establish a small balcony garden or to connect with nature [1]. We don't always have enough time or energy to water our lawn and flower plants; additionally, there can be succulents, money plants, and various indoor and outdoor plants. It is our small attempt to make your leisure-time hobby easier, more enjoyable, and smarter. We are introducing an IoT and artificial intelligence based smart irrigation and gardening system where you will find smart ways to water your plants, receive periodic updates and notifications, and know the state of the climate [2].

What is IoT

IoT, or the internet of things, is changing the way we live and how we act and react. Whether you have a smart air conditioner that you can control with your smartphone, a smart car that calculates the quickest route, or a smart watch that tracks your daily activities, the Internet of Things (IoT) is a gateway network for connecting your devices [3]. These devices gather and share data on the other operator, their surroundings, and their usage. Every physical thing you use every day contains sensors, including your cell phone, an electric motor, a traffic light, a bar code sensor, and other objects. This sensor continuously reports the divisions' operational status. However, this data gathering will be advantageous to us. All of these devices can connect to the Internet of Things (IoT) platform and dump their data into a single language so they can communicate with one another. Data is produced by several sensors and delivered to an IoT platform, where it is safely combined with data from other sources. Important information is taken from the data as needed after additional processing. The data is then shared with other devices for an improved user experience, better automation, and greater efficiency [4].

What is artificial intelligence

The replication of human intelligence functions by machines, particularly computer systems, is known as artificial intelligence. Expert systems, natural language processing, speech recognition, and machine vision are some examples of specific AI applications [5]. We have employed a variety of sensors in this system that can determine when to water plants and make irrigation decisions on their own [6].

Our System

Now let's get to the fun part. Several hardware, including a NodeMCU ESP8266, a 5V water motor, a 9V battery, a relay module, a rain sensor, a temperature and humidity sensor (DHT11), a soil moisture sensor (V1.2), and a soil moisture sensor (YL-69), that we use to turn on and off the water motor and feed water to the plants, have been employed in the construction of our IoT-based smart irrigation system. Our own Android app and the open-source Internet of Things (IoT) framework NodeMCU are both in charge of controlling everything. Most importantly, we are providing a full package of plant care using our Android application. This will be so helpful for fancy gardeners [7].

Objectives

- To control the irrigation system and monitoring the climate from anywhere in the world are both possible.
- To make easy the lives of the gardeners.
- To present automatic and manual irrigation system that will save time.
- To supply efficient irrigation methods that save time.
- To maintain the entire garden, but it also needs to be update frequently.
- To ensure that every output from the machine is entirely accurate, we must keep updating the system.
- To expand the functionality, and we must work more closely with the Internet of Things (IoT), microcontrollers, digital logic circuits, deep learning, machine learning, digital image processing, and artificial intelligence (AI).
- To provide pleasant outcomes, facilitating smooth current flow, and minimizing water loss.
- To improve the efficiency of the irrigation and smart gardening systems.

Problem Statement

- Most of the time, when people are in tour, there is no other option to water the plants, and other alternatives are costly and unsafe [8].
- The majority of smart devices, whether agents, gadgets, or systems, have complex and expensive user interfaces, are not portable, and are hard to comprehend by regular people [9].
- Many studies have been conducted to determine why the watering system is automatic; if the soil is dry, the system will automatically water the plants; however, not every plant requires the same amount of water, and sometimes a lot of water is harmful to plants. Over-watering causes plant death [10].
- The majority of individuals cannot afford the full system because of its high cost. If it has a walking robot with a built-in camera for monitoring, a camera to identify plants, equipment to scan for diseases and pests, a watering system, a sensor to detect soil minerals and organic matter, and a function to care for outdoor plants, additionally, a large space is needed for this kind of system [11].

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Related Work

- V. Rafi proposed a system for automated irrigation that could use soil moisture and rain sensors to help optimize the irrigation process [12]. The proposed system was capable of measuring the water content of the soil and detecting rainfall. It was also able to determine the amount of water needed for irrigation and control the pumps accordingly. The proposed system could be used for both large-scale and small-scale irrigation, and it could be connected to a central computer for monitoring and control. The proposed system could be used to reduce water wastage and water stress in agricultural areas and was expected to be cost-effective. As we previously mentioned, overwatering is harmful to plants. In every automatic system, there is an issue of overwatering. In huge agricultural fields, an automatic system is suitable. However, an automatic system is not appropriate for all times in rooftop or balcony gardens.
- Rajashekar Reddy Chinta proposed a low cost smart irrigation control system [13]. They used essential smart irrigation tools, including ultraviolet (UV) light disinfection, which is one water treatment system that can be used to remove most forms of microbiological contamination from water. Their system is automatic and made for the farms, fields, and crops. They proposed a low-cost smart irrigation control system that helps farmers maximize their water usage efficiency. This system is designed to automate the irrigation process and maximize crop yield by providing farmers with real-time information about their soil moisture levels. The

system is based on an Arduino board and a soil moisture sensor. The Arduino board is programmed to send alerts to farmers when the soil moisture levels drop below a certain threshold.

The system can be used to control irrigation pumps and valves, thus allowing farmers to save water, reduce labor and energy costs, and maximize crop yield. The system is also capable of controlling the frequency and duration of irrigation cycles, thus optimizing the crop yield. Additionally, the system can be used to measure the amount of water used for irrigation, thus helping farmers optimize their water usage.

- Syed Musthak Ahmed has proposed a revolutionary IoT-based automatic plant watering system through soil moisture sensing a technique to support farmers' cultivation in rural India [14]. Their system is aimed at improving the productivity of the farmers by providing them with an automated and efficient way to monitor and water their crops. The system works by using IoT sensors to monitor the soil moisture levels and then automatically triggering the irrigation systems to water the crops when the soil moisture levels fall below a certain threshold. This helps conserve water and improve the yields of the crops. The system also provides farmers with real-time data about their soil moisture levels, allowing them to make informed decisions about their irrigation practices. The proposed system is designed to be low-cost and easy to use, making it accessible for rural farmers. It is also designed to be energy efficient and can be powered by solar energy, making it a sustainable solution for farmers. Overall, their system has the potential to revolutionize farming in rural India by providing farmers with an efficient and automated way to monitor and water their crops. It could potentially lead to higher crop yields and improved livelihoods for farmers.

Finally, their system is an automatic irrigation system using Blynk which is an IoT platform for Android smartphones that is used to control Arduino, Raspberry Pi and NodeMCU via the Internet.

- Ravi Kishore Kodali proposed "A Low-Cost Smart Irrigation System Using MQTT Protocol" as a way to reduce water waste and improve crop yields [15]. They used MQTT as a messaging protocol for IoT. Used extra LDR sensor to measure the light intensity. The system uses a low-cost soil moisture sensor and an Arduino microcontroller to measure the soil moisture and transmit this information to a web server using the MQTT protocol. The system also includes an Android app, which can be used to control the irrigation system remotely. The system can be used to automatically turn on and off an irrigation system based on the soil moisture levels and the user's preferences. The system also provides real-time feedback to the user to help them optimize their irrigation system for maximum efficiency. This system is a cost-effective and efficient way to improve crop yields by reducing water waste and increasing yields.

- Mubashir Ali IoT based smart garden monitoring system using NodeMCU microcontroller [16]. They have a TFT screen for showing the results of the moisture sensor, temperature sensor, and humidity sensor. However, the result is also visible on their Android application screen. On the basis of that TFT screen, they are claiming that it is a monitoring system.

This system utilizes a NodeMCU microcontroller and other sensors, such as soil moisture, temperature, and light sensors, to monitor the environmental conditions of a garden. This system then transmits the collected data to a cloud platform and displays it on a mobile application. The user can then view the environmental conditions of their garden and take necessary actions if required. This system can also alert the user when the soil moisture level is too low or the temperature is too high. The NodeMCU microcontroller is programmed to send alerts to the user via SMS and email in such cases. The system also has an integrated irrigation system that can be controlled remotely. This system can be used to water the plants in the garden at pre-set times. Through the mobile app, the user can also monitor the energy consumption of the system. This system is an ideal solution for gardeners who wish to monitor and manage their garden remotely.

2.2 Gap Analysis

- There is no study on merging identifications based on deep learning with IoT based smart gardening [17].
- Many researchers around the world have tried to develop smart irrigation systems based on the Internet of Things for huge agricultural lands, not for small or mini plant-pots.
- Due to limitations on customization, the Blynk app is challenging to use.
- Water loss and excessive watering, which is bad for plants, are problems with the automatic irrigation system.

- The majority of the systems are complicated to understand and not portable for small balconies and rooftop gardens.
- The monitoring systems are not properly monitored because there are no cameras, no way to catch shady characters, and no traps to collect dangerous insects.

III. METHODOLOGY

3.1 Hardware

Our Internet of Things (IoT)-based smart irrigation and gardening solution provides comfortable garden and agricultural field watering [18]. It is a sophisticated technology that is reachable from any location on Earth. We first measured the soil moisture using a soil moisture sensor and the NodeMCU ESP8266, an open-source IoT platform. We employed two different kinds of soil moisture sensors. For automatic watering systems, soil moisture sensor model number YL-69 is used; for manually operated systems, soil moisture sensor model number V1.2 is used. The DHT11 temperature and humidity sensor is the system's most crucial component. In order to ascertain the precise amount of moisture that plants need, DHT11 is used to screen the state of the environment and climate. The environment's temperature pattern will aid the gardener in selecting the right kind of plant to cultivate this season. To determine when to water a plant and when not to, humidity is crucial. A crucial role is played by the rain sensor. Pumping is not necessary if it is raining because overwatering is poisonous to plants. To control the water motor, we utilized a relay module. Finally, our irrigation system is equipped to water both large agricultural regions and any rooftop or balcony garden [19].

3.2 NodeMCU ESP8266

NodeMCU 8266 is a low-cost, open-source IoT platform [20]. It is based on the ESP8266 WiFi SoC and consists of a full-featured ESP8266-based microcontroller with integrated Wi-Fi and several GPIOs. It is one of the most popular IoT development boards on the market today. It supports both the Arduino IDE and Lua scripting for programming.

3.1.2 Soil Moisture Sensor YL-69

The soil moisture level may be efficiently monitored and maintained by using a soil moisture sensor (YL69) in an IoT-based automatic watering system with an ESP8266 [21]. Because the YL69 sensor contains an integrated analog-to-digital converter, it can measure the soil moisture content and send the information to the ESP8266. With the use of this information, the ESP8266 may be configured to turn on the irrigation system automatically based on the moisture content of the soil. If the soil moisture level drops below a predetermined level, the irrigation system can be programmed to turn on. The sensor can also be used in conjunction with other sensors, such as temperature and humidity sensors, to provide a more complete picture of the state of the soil and enable more precise irrigation system control.

3.1.3 Soil Moisture Sensor V1.2

V1.2 For manual irrigation system control, we employed a soil moisture sensor. The user can water a plant whenever and from anywhere they like with the aid of the soil moisture sensor V1.2. A high-precision, portable, and reasonably priced soil moisture monitoring tool is the Soil Moisture Sensor V1.2 [22]. It allows customers to more effectively monitor the health of their plants and soil by measuring the amount of water in the soil using a unique polymer film. The gadget has a digital temperature sensor, and it can be used outside thanks to its waterproof construction. The sensor works with both Arduino and Raspberry Pi boards and is powered by a 3.3-volt battery. Additionally, it features a 4-pin Grove connector, which makes connecting to other devices simple. With a resolution of 0.1%, the instrument offers a detection range of 0–10%. It is appropriate for long-term use because of its low power consumption.

3.1.4 Temperature and Humidity Sensor (DHT11)

In irrigation systems, temperature and humidity sensors are used to keep track of soil moisture, temperature, and humidity levels. When and how much water should be used to water the plants can be decided using this information. This could improve crop yields and aid in water conservation [23]. It also helps to avoid over- or under-watering, which can endanger crops and plants. To monitor the environment's temperature and humidity, we used the DHT 11 temperature and humidity sensor. Thus, we are able to use the environment to decide when to water and when not to water our plants. A popular temperature and humidity sensor for DIY

and educational projects is the DHT11. It is inexpensive. With its single-wire serial interface, connecting to a microcontroller is simple. The DHT11 has a quick response time and reading accuracy of $\pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ for temperatures and $\pm 5\%$ for humidity. The sensor can be directly powered from 3V to 5.5V and is digital. Additionally, it uses little power, which makes it perfect for battery-powered applications. For a variety of uses, including weather monitoring, HVAC systems, and home automation, the DHT11 is a well-liked option.

3.1.5 Rain Sensor

A rain sensor must first be linked to the ESP8266 board in order to be used with an IoT-based irrigation system. The user must then use the Arduino IDE to program the ESP8266 in order to read the sensor's data. This information ought to be kept in a user-accessible database [24]. The system should employ a threshold for rainfall that the user specifies in the program to decide when to turn on the irrigation system. The ESP8266 will alert the irrigation system to shut off if the amount of rain reaches the threshold. On the other side, the ESP8266 will trigger the irrigation system to switch on if the rainfall falls below the threshold. In order to make sure that the plants only get the right amount of water, an ESP8266-based irrigation system can use a rain sensor. A rain sensor is a crucial part of an ESP8266-based Internet of Things irrigation system.

3.1.6 Relay Module

A crucial element of an IoT-based irrigation system powered by the ESP8266 is the relay module. It is an electrically powered switch that may regulate the water supply to the plants when actuated by the ESP8266. The water pump and solenoid valves that regulate the water flow to the plants are often turned on and off using this. The relay module can be used to control the irrigation system from any location with an internet connection because it is made to be remotely triggered. Relay modules are electrical parts that are used to manage water pumps. A relay switch, an electromagnetically powered switch used to regulate electrical flow, and a set of terminals, which are used to attach the relay switch to the water pump, are the typical components. The water pump's power is turned on and off using a relay module, which enables precise control of the water pump's flow rate and speed. Additionally, it is utilized to lower the amount of power needed by the water pump and protect it against power surges and overcurrent. It can be used in a variety of applications, including agricultural, commercial, and residential water systems. It is a crucial part for controlling water pumps [25].

3.1.7 9V Battery

An IoT-based irrigation system with an ESP8266 relay module and a 5V DC water motor is a wonderful fit for a 9V battery. The 9V battery offers a dependable and affordable energy source and can supply the motor and relay with the necessary power. The 9V battery has the benefit of providing power to the system for lengthy periods of time, enabling the motor to keep running at its peak efficiency. The battery is a great option for an IoT-based irrigation system because it is simple to replace and maintain [26].

3.1.8 5V Water Motor

A 9V battery powers the 5V water motor, which is coupled to the relay module by the ESP8266. Since the 5V water motor has a relatively low power need, it is perfect for continuous usage in an irrigation system. Additionally, it has the ability to deliver a constant water flow, enabling precision irrigation of plants. The 5V water motor is excellent for outdoor applications because it is very dependable and corrosion-resistant. As a result, it may be applied in a range of settings and offer an effective and trustworthy irrigation system [27].

3.1.9 System Diagram

A complete irrigation system can be built using a system diagram consisting of a NodeMCU ESP8266, moisture sensor V1.2, moisture sensor YL-69, rain sensor, relay module, 5V DC water motor, and DHT11. The moisture sensors and rain sensors can provide input to the NodeMCU, and the relay module can be utilized to switch on or off the water motor. While the moisture sensors can be used to track the moisture content of the soil, the DHT11 can be used to measure the temperature and humidity of the surrounding air. The irrigation process may then be automated with this method, ensuring that the soil is properly hydrated to promote the healthiest possible plant growth. The figure of system diagram is given below:

Figure 1: System Diagram

The following is how the wire connections are made:

- (+) of the DHT11 goes into 3V3 of the NodeMCU.
- (-) of the DHT11 goes into GND of the NodeMCU.
- DATA of the DHT11 goes into D1 of the NodeMCU.
- Vcc of the relay module goes into 3V3 of the NodeMCU.
- GND of the relay module goes into GND of the Node MCU.
- Control input of the relay module goes into D7 of the NodeMCU.
- NO of the relay module goes into (+) of the battery.
- COM Of the relay module goes into (+) of the 5V DC water motor.
- (-) of the 5V DC water motor goes into (-) of the battery.
- D0 of the moisture sensor YL-69 goes into D6 of the NodeMCU.
- GND of the moisture sensor YL-69 goes into GND of the NodeMCU.
- Vcc of the moisture sensor YL-69 goes into 3V3 of the NodeMCU.
- D0 of the rain sensor goes into D5 of the NodeMCU.
- Vcc of the rain sensor goes into 3V3 of the NodeMCU.
- GND of the rain sensor goes into GND of the NodeMCU.
- D0 of the rain sensor goes into D5 of the NodeMCU.
- GND of the moisture sensor V1.2 goes into GND of the NodeMCU.
- A0 of the moisture sensor V1.2 goes into A0 of the NodeMCU.
- Vcc of the moisture sensor V1.2 goes into 3V3 of the NodeMCU.

3.3 Android Application to Manage the Hardware

"Baganbilash" is the name of our Android application. With the Android app, we will manage the irrigation system and hardware.

Figure 2: Android Application to Manage the Hardware

3.2.1 Arduino

The ESP8266 and Arduino connection is a potent one that gives users the ability to perform a number of activities. Users can quickly and simply establish a wireless connection between the two devices to operate equipment, send data, and receive data from a distance. Either SPI or the serial port of the Arduino can be used to connect to this device. The ESP8266 may also be managed by Arduino, enabling users to configure a number of wireless protocols, including WiFi and Bluetooth. By connecting the two devices, users may use the Arduino's potent microcontroller to command the ESP8266 and develop creative creations. Users can view their projects remotely from any location in the world by using this connection to build a web server. Users can also benefit from the Arduino's ability to read and write data to and from the ESP8266, opening up a variety of opportunities for data transfer, monitoring, and control.

3.2.2 Firebase

How ESP8266 works with Firebase:

- A cloud-based application platform called Firebase gives online and mobile applications real-time data storage, authentication, and hosting services. It has grown to be a popular option for supplying power to software created with the ESP8266 microcontroller, a low-cost, low-power device that may be used to create a range of connected devices.
- Data may be stored and instantly synced between devices using Firebase. This makes it simple to develop robust apps that can react to data changes in a reliable and timely manner. For instance, Firebase can be used to automatically update the temperature reading in a web or mobile application when an ESP8266 device detects a change in the ambient temperature.
- Powerful authentication services are also offered by Firebase, which may be used to protect access to data and devices. OAuth, Facebook, Google, and 31 other means of authentication are supported by the Firebase API. This enables users to securely access data from their devices and makes it simple to integrate user accounts into ESP8266 applications.
- Finally, Firebase offers hosting services, which makes it simple to deploy an ESP8266-based application. With support for all major web browsers, the Firebase Hosting service offers a safe and dependable solution to host web apps.

IV. IMPLEMENTATION AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Implementation of Hardware

- Will use only one DHT11 temperature and humidity sensor and only one rain sensor for a single rooftop garden.
- Soil moisture sensor will apply for every same kind of plant.

Figure 3: Implementation of Hardware

4.2 Android Application Implementation

- First you need to open the application Baganbilash.
- In smart irrigation system you can control your hardware and get information which is sent by the sensors. This is our Android application, named "Baganbilash".

4.3 Cost Analysis

- This system is cost effective because the system can be controlled from any where of the world.
- Reduce the water wastage.

- Same kind of plant need only one soil moisture sensor.
- Our hardware cost is only Five thousand taka which is cheaper than worker of plant care.
- We are using single rain sensor, temperature sensor, humidity sensor and the number of moisture sensor is depends on your garden.

V. FUTURE WORK

- Setting up a substantial irrigation system for any type of land.
- To upgrade the infrastructure for vast agricultural fields.
- To enhance and add functionality to the water motors.
- Increasing the number of sensors to detect suspicious or thieving people at night.
- Including tools to trap dangerous insects in the field.
- Adding live assistance and instruction in smart agriculture to our offering.

VI. CONCLUSION

We have made an effort to simplify the gardeners' jobs. People who don't have time to garden or who wish to perform research on plants or crops will greatly benefit from this platform. It is simpler to monitor and modify your watering plan thanks to these systems' internet connectivity and ability to be controlled remotely. Sensors can be utilized with these systems to monitor soil and humidity levels, allowing you to water your plant just when it actually needs it. Additionally, you don't have to bother about manually turning them on or off because they may be set to turn on and off automatically. Additionally, you may set up these systems to alert you if the soil is too dry or if it is too hot or cold for your plants. Our developed system offers a fantastic resource for people who wish to plant trees, learn how to take care of them, prevent plant illnesses, and discover the soil's mineral composition. Finally, we believe that our smart irrigation and gardening systems powered by the Internet of Things plays an enormous role to eliminate guesswork from daily activities of farming, particularly in gardening watering.

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